

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

IRANIAN AND HITTITE-LUWIAN PARALLELS OF THE ARMENIAN WORDS *TAPAST*-‘CARPET’ AND *TAPAST*- ‘A KIND OF DEADLY PAIN, DISEASE’

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Abstract

The author discusses etymology of the Armenian word ‘*tapast*’ ‘cover, carpet’ and ‘*tapast*’ ‘a kind of deadly pain, decease’, that generally are considered to be Iranian loanword or of unknown origin.

We would like to indicate to the word ‘*tapašpa*’ in Hittite with meaning ‘a type of cloth or cover’ and *tapaš*- ‘fever, heat, an unknown decease’ that have no clear etymology in Hittite. We suppose that the Armenian words may have etymological connection with the Hittite ones as they have similar meaning, however Avestan *tapasti*- and Middle Persian (Pahlavi) *tapasta*- ‘carpet’ parallels cannot be ignored. As we see from semantic point of view there are three lexical parallels in Armenian, Hittite and Iranian with comparable sounding and meaning: Iranian *tapasti*- (‘fever’) - *tapasta* (‘carpet’), Armenian ‘*tapast*’ (‘fever, unknown decease’) and *tapast* (‘carpet, cloth’), Hittite *tapaš* (‘fever’, decease’ and *tapašpa*, *tapišša*, *tapašša*- (‘a type of clothing or cover’).

Both Armenian and Iranian parallels enable us to identify their matches in Hittite and other IE languages (Armenian and Iranian in this case) that have not been made so far and specify their meaning.

Keywords: Armenian, Iranian, Hittite-Luwian, *tapast*, *tapasti*, *tappiša*, ^{TÜG}*tapašpa*, *Spring Tapas*

Preface

We discuss in this article the etymology of the words *tapast*- ‘cover’, and *tapast*- a kind of deadly disease’, which in general have been considered Iranian loanwords in Armenian or of unknown origin. It should be noted that there are a number of words in the Armenian language, the Iranian origin of which has long been circulated in science, but the latter also have their Hittite-Luwian parallels. The above-mentioned words in the Armenian language belong to this stratum.

Linguistic Analysis

The Armenian has a word ^{TÜG}*tapast* meaning ‘cover, carpet’, one of the oldest versions of which is *tapastak* ‘sofa’, fixed in ancient Armenian sources [2:374; 4:541].

The word *tapast* is considered to be an Iranian loanword by the Armenian linguists Hrachya Acharyan, Gevorg Jahukyan [6:548], Anahit Perikhanyan and others. According to Perikhanyan, Armenian has no suffix *-ast*, the Indo-European suffixes **-es-ti*, **-os-ti* become *-est*, *-ust* in Armenian. The researcher notes that in Indo-Iranian languages these two variants are reflected as *-asti*, and this suffix occurs very rarely as it lost productivity at a very early stage, indicating that this suffix occurs only in a few cases such as *gābhasti* ‘hand, trunk’ in Sanskrit, *tapasti* ‘fever’ in Avestan, from which derives the Armenian *tapast* with the same meaning, considered a Parthian loanword, as well as the Indo-Iranian *-asta*, found in the word *karasta*- ‘leather’ and *tapasta*- ‘carpet’ that also is present in Armenian as *tapast* meaning ‘carpet’ (considered to be a Parthian loanword in Armenian either) [10:58]. We would like to indicate here that according to our observations, there is a word *tapašpa* in Hittite meaning ‘a type of cloth or cover’, while the Hittite word *tapaš* ‘heat, fever, disease’ is believed to be its possible root. Both

the root *tapaš* and *tapašpa*- do not have an exact etymology in Hittite. *tapašpa* is found in Hittite inventory texts when listed among other pieces or types of clothing. For example as in the following passage: “five dresses, one of which *šuhru*, one *tapašpa*, two *kuašštu*, one *kušši*”. We also come across to the forms *tappiša*, *tapašša*, *tapiššan* in the texts. Grammatically, *tapašpa* can be interpreted as a word having collective meaning [13:124; 12:621f]¹. As known, this word *tapast* in Armenian is of Iranian origin, however, we would like to draw attention to the Hittite parallel of this word.

The next Armenian word is *tapast*- ‘a kind of deadly pain, disease’, the origin of which is unknown, according to G.Jahukyan [7:721], while A. Perikhanyan believes that it can be traced back to the Avestan language [10:58]. In Armenian, there is also a form *tapas*, ‘possibly meaning a kind of child's skin decease possibly having connection with *tapast*- [1:1015; 9:375]; even a hydronium *Spring Tapas* [2:374] curing this decease *tapas* [1:1015] has been preserved. *Spring Tapas*[11:21] was located in town *Arabkir* [5:42], province of Kharberd (Eastern Armenian, Ottoman Empire), where it existed, among several other springs such as *Doł*, *Kat nalbyur*, *Khalil Chavush*. To add, springs with curing waters related with names of diseases, e.g., *Kosi albyur* [3:100] ‘Itchspring’, *Akanjac avi albyur* [3: 107] ‘Ear pain spring’, etc. are also recorded in Armenian.

The Hittite has a word *tapaš* ‘fever, heat, an unknown disease’, again without an exact etymology [13:124]. We assume that the Armenian *tapas* is related to the Hittite word, as they are semantically identical, however the Avestan parallel *tapesti*- ‘fever’ cannot be ignored. Besides, it is known that the word *tap* ‘heat, warmth’ is considered an Iranian loanword [2: 371; 6: 548] in the Armenian language.

¹ Siegelová J., KUB XLII59Rs.16.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that in the case of these semantically related words, in Armenian, Hittite-Iranian languages, it is possible to group identical word pairs with the same meaning. Iranian: *tapasti-* 'fever', *tapasta-* 'carpet' - Armenian: *tapast-* 'fever' and *tapast-* 'carpet, cover', Hittite: *tapaš-* 'fever, heat, disease' and *tapašpa, tapišša, tapašša-* 'a type of cloth or cover'. These parallels in Armenian and Iranian languages give us a possibility not only to find out their parallels of Hittite words existing in other Indo-European languages, which have not been discussed so far, but also to clarify the meaning of the latter.

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STRUCTURAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ETHNO-TOPONYMS OF KANGARLI DISTRICT

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Abstract

At present one of the main problems that toponymy face with is the study of ethnonym-based place names spread in different regions of the world. The semantic analysis of such toponyms, as well as the study of the features of their formation is actual in terms of studying the ethnogenesis of nations and the historical ethno-demographic composition of the population in different regions. The article deals with the Kangarli region, located in the northwest of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, located near the most ancient centers of civilization in the Middle East and distinguished by its unique features

In order to reveal scientific truths, both toponyms were analyzed in depth, both structurally and semantically, and comparative analyzes and analogies were made between them. A multidisciplinary approach to the issue was put forth for a more in-depth analysis of ethno-toponyms. Such analyzes make it necessary to study ethno-toponyms not only in terms of linguistics, but also in the historical context of ethnogenesis.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, Kangarli, ethno-toponyms, etymology, structural-semantic analysis.